

Childhood Trauma, Time Management Disposition and Academic Self-efficacy in High School Students

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Academic self-efficacy is very important for high school students. Studies show that academic self-efficacy is influenced by childhood trauma and personality, especially childhood trauma, which may even affect the formation and development of individual personality. Time management disposition is a kind of personality based on time perspective. This study aimed to explore the relationship between childhood trauma, especially psychological abuse and neglect, time management disposition, and academic self-efficacy in high school students. Two hundred and eighty-three high school students in two Chinese rural public secondary schools of Gansu Wuwei have measured their childhood trauma (Child Psychological Abuse and Neglect Scale), time management disposition (Adolescents Time Management Disposition Inventory), academic self-efficacy (Academic Self-efficacy Inventory). A structural equation model was performed to analyze the mediator effect of Time Management Disposition for the relationship between childhood trauma and academic self-efficacy. High school students have a prevalence of psychological abuse and neglect. Specific forms of trauma (neglect) can significantly negatively predict academic self-efficacy and childhood neglect can directly affect academic self-efficacy through time management disposition. The neglected experience of childhood may affect the time personality of high school students, which will affect their confidence in academic ability.

Keywords: CHILDHOOD TRAUMA, TIME MANAGEMENT DISPOSITION, ACADEMIC SELF-EFFICACY, HIGH SCHOOL STUDENT, NEGLECT

Introduction

Self-efficacy is an important concept proposed by the famous psychologist Bandura in 1977. He describes self-efficacy as the expectation if one can operate action in a specific situation and a powerful force in human operation. It plays an inestimable and irreplaceable value in the control and regulation of behavior. Bandura argues that there are different requirements of the individual's ability in different areas. As a result, individuals have different subjective judgments of abilities and confidence when they are faced with different situations. Academic Self-efficacy is a concept in the field of learning. Bandura(1977a) defines academic self-efficacy as the manifestation of self-efficacy in the field of learning and refers to learners' having the ability or skills to complete the task of learning to assess the degree of self-confidence, which is the individual to control their own learning behavior. High school is an important stage in a person's life, and learning is the main activity of high school students in school and also the basis of their physical and mental development (Wang, & Su, 2013). Those with higher self-efficacy are proposed to have higher aspirations, stronger commitments to their goals, and recover more quickly from setbacks than those lower in self-efficacy (Fast et al., 2010). Since it is particularly important to improve academic self-efficacy for high school students

Academic self-efficacy has a wide range of effects on high school students' academic performance (Ahmadi, Najafi, & Khanekhesi, 2014), academic motivation (Aydin, 2015), and mental health (Najafi, & Foadjang, 2007). According to social learning theory, people's self-efficacy beliefs about their talents and abilities are mainly established through the performance information provided by the four sources: personal acquired experiences, alternative experiences, and verbal explanations, physiological and emotional states (Bandura, 1977b). Therefore, academic self-efficacy is also affected by these four factors, especially an individual's already acquired experience. As attention to the potential negative outcomes of childhood trauma has grown, so have called for schools to take an active role in supporting students experiencing trauma. Childhood trauma as an environmental risk factor, early traumatic experience may affect the individual's experience of reality and cognitive attitude (Wei-Wei, Shao-Jia, Wei, & Peng, 2013). Moreover, the more severe the abuses of children are, the worse their emotional feeling to the outside world is, and the easier it is to form a negative and pessimistic emotional experience (Yang & Zhu, 2009). Therefore, academic self-efficacy may be affected by childhood experiences, especially the negative impact of childhood trauma. Four types of maltreatment in childhood, namely, physical abuse, sexual abuse, psychological abuse, and neglect, have received wide recognition in the literature (Barnett, Manly, & Cicchetti, 1993; Leeb, Paulozzi, Melanson, Simon, & Arias, 2008; Manly, Kim, Rogosch, & Cicchetti, 2001; Payne, Gainey & Carey, 2007). Currently, the studies of child abuse mainly focus on physical abuse and sexual abuse, and there were few types of research on psychological abuse and neglect (Xie, Tang, & Chang, 2008). Psychological abuse and neglect often leave more irreparable scars on children's psychology (Sanders, & Becker-Lausen, 1995). Psychological abuse mainly stems from the responsibility, obligation, and closeness of the child, which is continuous, repetitive, and inappropriate behavior. and greatly

undermines children's social, cognitive, and emotional development. However, these behaviors do not involve physical or sexual contact with children, including three types but include scolding, intimidation, and interference. The definition of neglect is as follows: Ignorance is the long-term neglect of the child's basic needs by the caregiver, and it harms or impairs the child's healthy development. The basic needs involve appropriate emotional communication, education, protection, housing, clothing, food, and health care. Including emotional neglect, educational neglect, and physical/supervisory neglect (Deng, Pan, Tang, Yuan, Xiao, 2007). A longitudinal study on self-efficacy shows a weak negative longitudinal association between self-efficacy and exposure to trauma (Bosmans et al., 2013).

Personality is another important factor that affects academic self-efficacy (Giunta et al., 2013; Lin, Lu, Chen, & Chen, 2014). Huang et al. (2001) defined the concept of time management as a personality trait, which can be reflected in the way one utilizes and control time. The Time Management Disposition (TMD) includes the sense of time value, the sense of time efficacy, and the sense of time control. And the sense of time control is the individuals' ability and the notion of using and controlling time through a series of explicit activities, which performs as the time control activities in an individual's subjective assessment of their own. Huang developed Adolescence Time Management Disposition Scale (ATMD) (Huang, & Zhang, 2001). The study found that time management disposition and its dimensions have a significant positive correlation with academic self-efficacy in high school students (Xiao & Qing, 2008).

Childhood trauma is a major public health problem that has an impact on personality development, but only a few studies examined the association between exposure to trauma and personality. Studies have shown that significant positive correlations existed between Childhood trauma and EPQ-N, EPQ-P scores in Chinese adolescents (Li, Wang, Hou, Wang, & Wang, 2014). Time management disposition is a kind of personality based on time perspective, but we don't know whether the current childhood trauma, especially psychological abuse and neglect may affect the time management disposition. Individuals who experience childhood trauma often form a negative avoidance coping strategy (Cantón-Cortés, Cantón, Justicia, & Cortés, 2011). And individuals who experience childhood trauma, especially psychological abuse and neglect tend to be immersed in past negative emotions, feel the time is too slow, often choose a way to escape, in this case, they would reduce the value of time, not very good control of their time, and effectively manage their time (Cantón-Cortés, Cantón, Justicia, & Cortés, 2011). At present, we don't know the relationship between childhood trauma, especially psychological abuse and neglect, time management disposition, and academic self-efficacy in high school students. Therefore, we would like to explore relations. We hypothesize the childhood abuse and neglect could significantly negatively affect academic self-efficacy, at the same time, time management disposition to play a mediating role. Two hundred and eighty-three high school students completed three investigations and researches.

Materials and methods

2.1 Participants

Data were collected through convenience sampling in two Chinese rural public secondary schools in the district of Wuwei Gansu. Participants included 283 students (172 males and 111 females) of the 10th to 12th grades (10th: $N=84$, 29.7% 10th, 11th: $N=101$, 35.7%, 12th: $N=98$, 34.6%) with ages ranging from 14 to 19 years ($M = 16.68$, $SD = 0.96$; only 2 students had ages 14 years and 3 students had aged 19 years) lived in rural areas ($N = 212$; 74.9%).

2.2. Measures

2.2.1. Child Psychological Abuse and Neglect Scale

Chinese Child Psychological Abuse and Neglect Scale (C-CPANS) was developed by Deng et al., (2007). This scale is widely used for studies in the local context. The scale has asked students to recall the past family atmosphere and how parents treated them during their growth. This self-administered instrument includes 31 items and consists of two dimensions. Psychological abuse includes three sub-dimensions: scold, intimidation, and interference, and Neglect includes three sub-dimensions: emotional neglect, educational neglect, and physical/supervision ignore. The scale measured on a five-point scale (ranging from “no such situation” to “always”), scale average score ≥ 1 point as positive. The reliability and validity of the instrument were verified in this study involving 283 secondary students. A confirmatory factor analysis was conducted with C-CPANS. Model fit indices provided mixed results for the fit of the model within this sample, $\chi^2/df = 2.124$, $CFI = 0.988$, $NFI = 0.977$, $GFI = 0.983$, $RMSEA = 0.063$. The reliability coefficient of Cronbach's Alpha is 0.877.

2.2.2. Adolescents Time Management Disposition Inventory

Chinese Adolescents Time Management Disposition Inventory (C-ADTMDI) was developed by Huang, & Zhang (2001). The Adolescence Time Management Disposition Inventory has been compiled According to the results of 1207 adolescents by exploratory factor analysis. The time management disposition has consisted of the sense of time value (it included social-oriented time value and individual-oriented time value), the sense of time control (it included setting goals, planning, priorities, time allocation, and feedback), and the sense of time efficacy (it included efficacy of time management and efficacy of time management behaviors). This self-administered instrument includes 44 items and is measured on a five-point scale (ranging from “Totally incompatible” to “Fully compliant”). A confirmatory factor analysis was conducted with C-ADTMDI. Model fit indices provided mixed results for the fit of the model within this sample, $\chi^2/df = 2.708$, $CFI = 0.962$, $NFI = 0.943$, $GFI = 0.954$, $RMSEA = 0.078$. The reliability coefficient of Cronbach's Alpha is 0.893.

2.2.3. Academic Self-efficacy Inventory

Chinese academic self-efficacy Inventory (C-ASEI) was developed by Liang (2002). This scale is widely used for studies in the local context. This self-administered instrument includes 22 items and consists of two independent dimensions. Learning ability self-efficacy and Learning behavior self-efficacy, Learning ability Self-efficacy refers to the individual's judgment and confidence in whether or not he or she has the

ability to successfully complete his studies, achieve good grades, and avoid academic failure. Learning behavior self-efficacy refers to the individual's confidence that one can take some learning methods to achieve certain learning goals. The scale was measured on a five-point scale (ranging from “Very agree” to “Very disagree”). This study has confirmed its reliability and validity. A confirmatory factor analysis was conducted with C-ASEI. Model fit indices provided mixed results for the fit of the model within this sample, $\chi^2/df=1.766$, $CFI=0.907$, $NFI=0.912$, $GFI=0.909$, $RMSEA=0.052$. The reliability coefficient of Cronbach's Alpha is 0.747.

2.3. Statistical analysis of data

Preliminary data analyses were conducted to analyze the socio-demographic characteristics of the subjects. Then, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was used to examine the validity of the questionnaire. The reliability of the factors was investigated with Cronbach's alpha. Pearson's correlation analysis was used to define the strength of the association among CPAN, ADTMD, and ASE, and the mediated effects of ADTMD on CPAN and ASE. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS for Windows version 22.0 and AMOS 21.0. *P*-values <0.05 were considered statistically significant.

3. Results

3.1. Descriptive analysis

The positive detection rate of psychological abuse or neglect was 49.8%. The High-Low-27-per-cent group method was used to divide psychological abuse and neglect into high groups and low groups (Fan, 1954), and then the differences in time management disposition and academic self-efficacy were examined by using an independent sample *t*-test. The results showed that there was no significant difference in all the dimensions of Time Management Disposition and academic self-efficacy between the high and low groups of psychological abuse, but Neglect had significant differences in all the dimensions of Time Management Disposition and academic self-efficacy. High-school students who scored lower scores than those who scored higher scored significantly higher in time value, time control, time efficacy, learning ability self-efficacy, and learning behavior self-efficacy.

Table 1 The differences in the time management tendency and academic self-efficacy between high and low groups of childhood trauma.

		Time value	Time control	Time efficacy	Learning ability self-efficacy	Learning behavior self-efficacy
Psychological Abuse	Low (N=83)	3.57±0.544	3.37±0.4	3.57±0.4	3.49±0.5	3.21±0.3
	High (N=82)	3.66±0.557	3.30±0.5	3.58±0.4	3.50±0.5	3.28±0.4
<i>t</i>		-1.091	1.060	-0.015	-0.135	-1.275
Neglect	Low (N=81)	3.82±0.505	3.51±0.4	3.64±0.5	3.56±0.5	3.32±0.4
	High	3.55±0.5	3.14±0.5	3.48±0.4	3.34±0.5	3.17±0.3

	(N=82)	49						
<i>t</i>		3.233**	5.221***	2.449*		2.764**		2.572*

Note: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Pearson's correlation analysis of the C-CPAN, C-ADTMD, and C-ASE has revealed that Neglect was negatively related to all the dimensions of Time Management Disposition and academic self-efficacy, and Psychological Abuse was negatively related to time control but not related to time value, time efficacy, Learning ability self-efficacy, and Learning behavior self-efficacy; time value, time control, and time efficacy was positively related to Learning ability self-efficacy and Learning behavior self-efficacy.

Table 2 Descriptive and correlations between Psychological Abuse and Neglect, ADTMD and ASE

	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	0.83	0.51	1	0.563**	0.024	-0.164**	-0.050	-0.029	0.020
2	0.82	0.50	0.563**	1	-0.150*	-0.312**	-0.131*	-0.164**	-0.134*
3	3.65	0.55	0.024	-0.150*	1	0.474**	0.518**	0.312**	0.292**
4	3.32	0.45	-0.164**	-0.312**	0.474**	1	0.698**	0.455**	0.387**
5	3.57	0.42	-0.050	-0.131*	0.518**	0.698**	1	0.482**	0.312**
6	3.45	0.5	-0.029	-0.164**	0.312**	0.455**	0.482**	1	0.253**
7	3.24	0.349	0.020	-0.134*	0.292**	0.387**	0.312**	0.253**	1

Note: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$. Psychological Abuse= 1, Neglect= 2, Time value= 3, Time control= 4, Time efficacy= 5, Learning ability self-efficacy= 6, Learning behavior self-efficacy= 7.

3.2 Structural model

Structural equation modeling was performed to analyze the relationship between Neglect and academic ASE in the first model and the relationship among Neglect, ADTMD, and ASE in the second model. A negative correlation was observed between Neglect and ASE without ADTMD (standardized regression weight=0.333, $p=0.004$) (Figure 1A). The model fit indices were $\chi^2/df = 0.843$, $CFI=1.000$, $NFI=0.989$, $GFI=0.995$, $RMSEA=0.000$. When ADTMD was included in the model, the direct effects of Neglect and ASE were not significant (standardized regression weight=-0.031, $p=0.726$). However, Neglect significantly negatively affected ADTMD (standardized regression weight=-0.315, $p<0.001$). As for the total effects, the Neglect has exhibited indirect effects on ASE through ADTMD as a mediator (Figure 1B). The model fit indices were $\chi^2/df = 2.272$, $CFI=0.970$, $NFI=0.949$, $GFI=0.968$, $RMSEA=0.067$. Specifically, in both models educational neglect has shown more influence on the latent variable, the results of the structural equation modeling have confirmed that ADTMD was a complete mediator of the relationship between Neglect and ASE.

Fig. 1. Structural equation model of the relationship between Neglect ADTMD and ASE. ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

This study is the first to use standardized instruments to examine the relationship between childhood trauma and academic self-efficacy, and the mediating role of time management disposition in high school students. Our findings indicate that high school students have high psychological abuse in our subjects. There is no significant difference in all dimensions of Time Management Disposition and academic self-efficacy between the high and low groups of psychological abuse, but contrary, neglect and specific forms of trauma (Neglect) can significantly negatively predict academic self-efficacy, and childhood neglect can directly affect academic self-efficacy through time management disposition.

The high positive rate of psychological abuse and neglect may indicate the prevalence of childhood psychological abuse and neglect in high school students (Zou, Liu, Zhu, Guo, & Shen, 2010). This may be due to psychological abuse and neglect is unconscious of the purpose of the act and the implicitness of the behavioral result and it is often overlooked by people (Qing-Wei, Ai-shu, & Ji-Chao, 2016). It has a profound effect on the psychological development of individuals, and many psychological problems or mental disorders are closely related to early childhood trauma (Choi et al., 2015; Yan, & Xian, 2005).

Research shows that childhood trauma experience would disrupt the development of self-associated cognitive components will directly influence an individual's negative evaluation and form negative self mode, while negative self-cognition affects an individual's perception of later interpersonal relationships (Psydy, & Prout, 2002; Yan, 2017). Soffer et al. (2008) found that childhood abuse and neglect have a negative influence on an individual's self-efficacy. Psychological abuse and neglect as an important aspect of childhood trauma also affect the individual's self-efficacy. The psychological abuse and neglect in the academic field will affect the individual's academic self-efficacy. However, our study only found that there was a significant difference in all the dimensions of time management disposition and academic self-efficacy between the high and low groups of neglect and negative correlation between neglect and academic self-efficacy in each dimension, that neglect can significantly negatively predict academic self-efficacy. Nevertheless, we not only didn't find a significant correlation between psychological abuse and academic self-efficacy but also didn't find the difference in all the dimensions of time management disposition and academic self-efficacy between the high and low groups of neglect. And we also did not find a negative correlation between psychological abuse and time value, time efficacy, learning ability self-efficacy. This may be due to the fact that child neglect is generally associated with poor developmental outcomes. Child neglect has severe, deleterious short-and long-term effects on children's cognitive, socio-emotional, and behavioral development (Hildyard, & Wolfe, 2002; Maughan, & Moore, 2010). With the development of society, people who have a responsibility and close relationship with children gradually change their way of getting along with their children, not just scolding, intimidating, and interfering with children in the past, giving them more material satisfaction, but more often neglecting their emotional, educational, physical/supervisory needs.

Neglect can significantly negatively predict academic self-efficacy, but the analysis of the mediating effect indicates that neglect has an indirect effect on academic self-efficacy through time management disposition. Namely, the experience of childhood neglect would have a negative impact on the formation and shaping of an individual's time personality, while time personality traits would also affect their academic performance and affect their academic self-efficacy. The study shows that childhood trauma is closely related to one's personality (Xiao, 2016). For example, childhood trauma alters the trajectory of adaptive personality development and promotes the development of maladaptive personality traits and personality disorders (Pos et al., 2016; Michelson, 2009). Time management disposition which is a special personality trait also affects the individual's academic self-efficacy (Kim, H. Y., Kim, S. Y., Seo, & So, 2011). That is, individuals who are better at managing time will have higher academic self-efficacy. When individuals experience more childhood neglect, they may be inclined to carry the burden of past experiences into the present, thus having an ongoing impact on their behavior. The more possible they are to repeatedly experience the feelings that have been ignored in the past, the more negative emotion would generate, and they have more choices to escape and negatively respond to deal with the neglected experience. When were

reduce their sense of time value, time control, and time efficacy? And personality influences an individual's academic self-efficacy in high school students (Caprara, Vecchione, Alessandri, Gerbino, & Barbaranelli, 2011), Students with high academic self-efficacy will have a stronger ability to manage their time. When high school students understand the value of time for themselves, they know how to allocate and use time rationally, and they have confidence in their own time management. When it is applied to learning, it is full of self-confidence in learning and proactive in learning behavior (Yang, 2010). Overall this also shows that childhood neglect has a profound impact on individuals and will have an important impact on the formation and development of individual personality, and this influence will progressively affect the self-evaluation of high school students in their studies.

Conclusion

Neglect can significantly negatively predict academic self-efficacy, but the analysis of the mediating effect indicates that neglect has an indirect effect on academic self-efficacy through time management disposition. Namely, the experience of childhood neglect would hurt the formation and shaping of an individual's time personality, while time personality traits would also affect their academic performance and affect their academic self-efficacy. The study shows that childhood trauma is closely related to one's personality (Xiao, 2016). For example, childhood trauma alters the trajectory of adaptive personality development and promotes the development of maladaptive personality traits and personality disorders (Pos et al., 2016; Michelson, 2009). Time management disposition which is a special personality trait also affects the individual's academic self-efficacy (Kim, H. Y., Kim, S. Y., Seo, & So, 2011). That is, individuals who are better at managing time will have higher academic self-efficacy. When individuals experience more childhood neglect, they may be inclined to carry the burden of past experiences into the present, thus having an ongoing impact on their behavior. The more possible they are to repeatedly experience the feelings that have been ignored in the past, the more negative emotion would generate, and they have more choices to escape and negatively respond to deal with the neglected experience. When there were reducing their sense of time value, time control, and time efficacy. And personality influences an individual's academic self-efficacy in high school students (Caprara, Vecchione, Alessandri, Gerbino, & Barbaranelli, 2011), Students with high academic self-efficacy will have a stronger ability to manage their time. When high school students understand the value of time for themselves, they know how to allocate and use time rationally, and they have confidence in their own time management. When it is applied to learning, it is full of self-confidence in learning and proactive in learning behavior (Yang, 2010). Overall this also shows that childhood neglect has a profound impact on individuals and will have an important impact on the formation and development of individual personality, and this influence will progressively affect the self-evaluation of high school students in their studies.

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